

Title of Impact Narrative: Impact Narrative: StrathE2E supports the scaling of Management Strategy Evaluation (MSE) and Ocean Literacy in the #AllAtlantic.		
Target: Ecosystem managers and regional decision-makers, Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOP).		
Period when the underpinning research was undertaken: 2020-2025		
Details of staff conducting the underpinning research from the submitting unit:		
Name(s): Michael Heath, Jack Laverick, Douglas Speirs	Role(s) (e.g. job title): Developers of StrathE2E & Leader of WP Modelling, (Mission Atlantic)	Period active in the project: 2020-2026
Period when the claimed impact occurred: 2024-2026		
Citation (this Impact Narrative): Laverick, J., Heath, M., & Speirs, D. (2024). Impact Narrative: StrathE2E supports the scaling of Management Strategy Evaluation (MSE) and Ocean Literacy in the #AllAtlantic. Zenodo, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15227796		

1 Summary of Outcome / Impact

- Mission Atlantic has **elevated TRL/SRL maturity from SRL4 to SRL8 in three years**, with multiple uses of Mobility Program Fellows to build model implementations in seven regional case studies in the Atlantic.
- **REACH** across the #AllAtlantic has grown **from 1 to 9 Regions**.

TESTIMONIAL

“It helps managers anticipate ecological shifts with evidence-based decision-making.”

Nana Adu-Agyei,
Manager Sakumono Ramsar Delta,
Ghana Forestry Commission.

- Significant **capacity building** has been achieved by training 45 Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOP) in partnership with ICES.dk. The number of institutions publishing research using StrathE2E has grown from two publishing institutions to nine throughout the Atlantic, representing a **tipping point in model uptake** by academia.
- Significant progress has been made exposing stakeholders to StrathE2E through **co-creation** of an interactive R-Shiny web app with a **diversity of end-users** including academics, fishermen associations (*MASTS Forum, 2022*, Celtic Sea workshops, 2022-2024), and Young Ocean Advocates (Youth4Ocean Forum, 2024). Sustained exposure of the tool (*Activity Log of demos 2022-2024*) has redefined next steps for improvement & development:

e.g. initial concerns by fishers that App could be misused to ban fisheries and negatively affect revenue, has since been addressed, and the model supported economic model development under UKRI’s [ECOWINGS Project](#).

2 Underpinning Research

Humanity makes myriad demands of Earth. Seven of nine planetary boundaries defining our safe living space on Earth have been breached. The most critical of these is biosphere integrity as climate shifts and people appropriate living resources. Fishing generates income for 10% of the global population and dietary protein for 3 billion people; but interacts with other management objectives. We also need offshore renewable energy projects, to reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and marine protected areas, to conserve biodiversity. Marine management is therefore a multi-dimensional problem requiring a systems approach. Only by considering everything at once can we correctly evaluate the choices we face and identify the optimum arrangement for people and their seas.

We developed the end-to-end ecosystem model StrathE2E to enable strategic thinking for ecosystem management in support of UN Strategic Development Goals 12, 13, and 14 (Sustainable Consumption and Production, Climate Action, Life Below Water). Sustainability can only be achieved through a systems approach where ecosystem management succeeds in satisfying multi-dimensional objectives.

Prior to Mission Atlantic there were two published regional implementations of StrathE2E; one for the North Sea and one for the Barents Sea in the Arctic. StrathE2E had been used in technical reports submitted to UK government but remained a technical tool for use by expert modelers.

As a direct result of Mission Atlantic, case study implementations of StrathE2E have been built throughout the ocean basin. There are now 12 regional models worldwide with Mission Atlantic supporting the necessary development work to represent oceanic islands, including Ascension Island, Saint Helena, and the Azores archipelago, and upwelling systems such as the Southern Benguela current and Senegal.

Mission Atlantic supported the creation of an online app linking directly to all the developed StrathE2E models, whether Atlantic or Arctic. The app facilitates real-time management strategy evaluation, allowing stakeholders and decision-makers to interactively engage in the modelling process and improve ocean literacy.

Overarching findings indicate that climate change threatens the future of fisheries and food webs throughout the Atlantic. This is generally driven by future declines in nutrient availability due to intensification of ocean thermal stratification. Ecosystem scale management strategies can offset some climate impacts, but these require engaging with tradeoffs against fisheries.

Mission Atlantic is on track to produce 11 StrathE2E academic publications. Seven of these have been led by research students and early career researchers. All research was supported by a writing workshop in June 2025 in Scotland. The studies are being collected as a themed set with the ICES Journal for Marine Science, with the first article already accepted for publication.

3 References to the research:

Heath M.R., Speirs D.C., Thurlbeck I, Wilson R.J.. StrathE2E2: An r package for modelling the dynamics of marine food webs and fisheries. *Methods Ecol Evol.*2021;12:280–287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13510>

Heath, M.R., Benkort, D., Brierley, A.S., Daewel, U., Laverick, J., Proud, R., and Speirs, D.C. (2022). Ecosystem approach to harvesting in the Arctic: walking the tightrope between exploitation and conservation in the Barents Sea. *Ambio*, 51: 456–470. Changing Arctic Ocean Special Issue. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01616-9>

Thorpe, R.B., Arroyo, N.L., Safi, G., Niquil, N., Heath, M., Pace, M.C. and Lynam, C.P. (2022). The response of North Sea ecosystem functional groups to warming and changes in fishing. *Frontiers in*

Marine Science 9:841909. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2022.841909

Thorpe, R.B., Heath, M.R. and Lynam, C.P. Can we use recovery timescales to define Good Environmental Status? (2023). Ecological Indicators 155, 110984, 17pp. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110984>

Laverick, J.H., Speirs, D.C. and Heath, M.R. (2025), Sea-Ice Retreat From the Northeast Greenland Continental Shelf Triggers a Marine Trophic Cascade. Glob Change Biol, 31
<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70189>

Olher, J.P., Laverick, J., Heath, M., Speirs, D.C. and Gasalla, M.A. (2026), Projecting biomass declines in the St Helena marine protected area food web due to climate change. Limnol. Oceanogr. Lett, 11: e70104. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lol2.70104>

Hatton, M., Laverick, J.H., Banas, N., Heath M.R. (2025), Ecosystem Recovery to Historical Targets Becomes Unattainable Under Modelled Fishing and Climate in the Barents Sea. arXiv.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.04806>

Genthon, T., Planque, B., Buttay, L., Laverick, J.H., & Heath, M.R. (2025). Forecasted climate change impacts on Norwegian Sea ecosystem and fisheries. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17131155>

4 Details of the IMPACT NARRATIVE:

To support ambitions to adopt an ecosystem-based approach to marine management we have been developing the end-to-end ecosystem model StrathE2E. As each new regional implementation of the model has become available, we have incorporated it into our interactive web-app. This activity supports stakeholders and decision-makers to interactively engage in the modelling process, while also improving ocean literacy.

We have delivered a program of demonstrations and training events to drive long-term impact from the research activities conducted under a variety of projects (Mission Atlantic, Seawise, One Ocean Hub, OceanICU, VALMAS, ECOWINGS, MiMeMo, and assorted PhD studentships). Since the start of Mission Atlantic there have been 15 presentations, app demonstrations, and training events from 2022 to 2026. These events have targeted a range of participants including: youth as Young Ocean Advocates from the Youth4Ocean Forum and Early Career Ocean Professionals in partnership with ICES, Industry representatives through the MASTS Fisheries Forum and the Celtic Sea Stakeholder Workshops, and government representative for Brazil, Saint Helena, and the UK Centre for Environment Fisheries and Aquaculture Science.

These activities have enabled the exchange of ideas between stakeholders and researchers, enabling a process of co-development of our web-app and engagement activities. Following the app demonstration at the MASTS Fisheries Forum in 2023, we received feedback from the fishing community that the app did not balance the impacts of livelihoods alongside ecosystem and the provisioning of food. We are now developing a coupled economic model under the ECOWINGS project to eventually link to the app. Following a demonstration to the EU's Youth4Ocean Forum in 2024 it was suggested the challenge for users won't be using the interface but rather interpreting the outputs. In 2025 we therefore complimented our demonstrations with explicit training activities in partnership with ICES (INTERDIS summer school, and at the ICEA ASC).

Future activities will support regional stakeholders to incorporate the results of eco-system scale trade-offs into the decision-making process. We also plan to refine the app to support Management Strategy Evaluation as detailed in MISSION ATLANTIC Deliverable D7.4 (cf CORDIS, Mission Atlantic Results), providing a screening tool to identify management strategies producing acceptable outcomes (under the VALMAS project).

5. Sources/ Evidence to corroborate the impact:

EVIDENCE OF POLICY CITATIONS:

- [Portfolio analysis, EU mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”](#), Publications Office of the European Union, 31 May 2023 cites Heath et al., 2021 (10.1111/2041-210X.13510)
- ICES Ecosystem Overviews: Greater North Sea Ecoregion, cites 10.3389/FMARS.2022.841909 in three consecutive reports on [26th Nov 2024](#), [30th Apr 2024](#), [15th Dec 2022](#)

The Response of North Sea Ecosystem Functional Groups to Warming and Changes in Fishing
 Robert B. Thorpe et al. (2022) *Frontiers in Marine Science*

Thorpe, R. B., Arroyo, N. L., Safi, G., Niquil, N., Preciado, I., Heath, M., Pace, M. C., and Lynam, C. P. 2022 The Response of North Sea Ecosystem Functional Groups to Warming and Changes in Fishing. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9: 841909. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.841909>

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- [Monitoring Report on the German Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change](#) (Germany Umwelt Bundesamt, 2023) cites Thorpe et al., 2022

The Response of North Sea Ecosystem Functional Groups to Warming and Changes in Fishing
 Robert B. Thorpe et al. (2022) *Frontiers in Marine Science*

“ Given the development of the mean surface temperatures along the North American Pacific coast well into the central Pacific ocean, it can be assumed that a warming regime has existed in that part of the Pacific since 2014. 75 ”

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75 Thorpe R.B., Arroyo N.L., Safi G., Niquil N., Preciado I., Heath M., Pace M.C., Lynam C.P. 2022: The Response of North Sea Ecosystem Functional Groups to Warming and Changes in Fishing. *Front. Mar. Sci., Sec. Marine Fisheries, Aquaculture and Living Resources*, Vol. 9 2022. doi:10.3389/fmars.2022.841909

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- [Marine biodiversity modelling study](#), Publications Office of the EU (2022) cites STRATHe2e Model in the context of implementation of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO). DTO is the desirable long-term e-infrastructure hosting for wide use of the model.

S <sc>trath</sc> E2E2: An <sc>r</sc> package for modelling the dynamics of marine food webs and fisheries
 Michael R. Heath et al. (2021) *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*

Heath, M. R., D. C. Speirs, I. Thuribeck, and R. J. Wilson. 2021. StrathE2E2: An R package for modelling the dynamics of marine food webs and fisheries. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 12:280–287.

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- ICES ASC public record:
<https://www.ices.dk/events/asc/2025/Pages/Forms/DispForm.aspx?ID=38#:~:text=Workshop%20on%20StrathE2E%3A%20End%2Dto%2Dend%20ecosystem,%E2%80%8BFriday%2019%20September%2010%3A00%E2%80%9315%3A00>
- Trainig [Workshop on the operational use of Food Web indicators and information \(WKFoodWeb; outputs from 2024 meeting\)](#)
- Training at MISSION ATLANTIC ICES/#InterDI2025 Summer School (official programme attended by 32 global attendees) and the embedded in the IEA e-Learning Course offered to 200+ applicants to the Summer School who could not be selected.
- StrathE2E Writing Retreat at the Burn, Scotland:
<https://pureportal.strath.ac.uk/en/projects/strathe2e-writing-retreat-for-mission-atlantic-additional-15000/>. Image attached.
- Evidence of App Demonstrations at the All-Atlantic Integrated Ecosystem Assessment Symposium
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gKGVFBO4dGo>.
- Overview of App Development <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2hJ8L3B0luY>.

APPENDICES (WORKING FILES FOR DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION):

6. Impact Pathway for 2026-2030:

- 2026: External Evaluation of Impact, by Saskia Walcott (Walcott Communications)
- 2026: Monitor Policy Citations, to deepen & diversify evidence of SCALE & SIGNIFICANCE
- 2026: engage North Sea Advisory Council (NSAC) and AC Conference, for end-use input
- 2027: Embed capabilities in case study partners, exploiting Mission Atlantic network.

--- end of #ImpactNarrative ---

Scan HERE for:

#All Atlantic
Impact Narratives

Mission Atlantic
website

IEA e-learning
Lessons

StrathE2E a marine end-to-end
ecosystem mode

